

Kongzhai Shrine of the Robe and Cap of Confucius in Shanghai

also known as “孔宅衣冠祠墓”

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Entry tags: Temple, shrines, Religious Group, China, Ritual centre, Religious Place, Monument, Chinese Religion, Confucianism, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult

A place called Kongzhai (Kong Residence), located in a once-rural area that is now within the borders of metropolitan Shanghai, formerly had a shrine for venerating Confucius (Kongzi / Master Kong) that was premised on the belief that a much later descendant had buried the ancient master's robe, cap, and jade ornaments there. Far from the region in North China where Confucius had lived or traveled and over 1000 years after his death, the alleged burial of these relics inspired local late Ming literati to construct a temple complex, centered on an above-ground "Tomb of the Robe and Cap" and a sacrificial hall with sculptural icons. At its height in the early Qing period, Kongzhai's structures, assorted visual images, and ritual artifacts supported its claim to be "Little Queli," a surrogate for the primordial temple, cemetery, and mansion of Confucius's Kong descendants in Qufu, Shandong. Scholars gathered there to experience his beneficent aura, and sacrifices to Confucius were performed with the same liturgy as in the official Confucian temples attached to government schools. Ambitious officials and local literati used their patronage and interactions with Kongzhai to enhance their own prestige and that of the humble locality. Eventually a line of Kong descendants was designated to take charge of sacrifices, as at other places where descendants had settled. Kongzhai's fortunes declined in the 19th century, and the fall of the Qing dynasty delegitimized Confucian ritualism. In the 20th century, Kongzhai became a target of Maoist campaigns against feudalism, superstition, and undesirable social classes, and it was conclusively destroyed in the Cultural Revolution. One building was later reconstructed in a park several miles away. All that remains on the former site itself are two very old ginkgo trees.

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1949 CE

Region: Greater Shanghai

Region tags: China, Shanghai

Greater Shanghai. The coordinates for the approximate location of Kongzhai are 31 11'50.18"N 121 06' 35.23"E.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: James A. Flath, *Traces of the Sage: Monument, Materiality, and the First Temple of Confucius*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 2016.

– Source 2: Huang, Chin-shing, *Confucianism and Sacred Space: The Confucian Temple from Imperial China to Today*. New York: Columbia University Press, 2021.

– Source 3: Thomas A. Wilson, ed., *On Sacred Grounds: Culture, Society, Politics, and the Formation of the Temple of Confucius*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Asia Center, 2002.

Notes: These sources are useful for understanding the larger contexts of Confucian religiosity that help make sense of Kongzhai.

– Source 1: Julia K. Murray, *The Aura of Confucius: Relics and Representations of the Sage at the Kongzhai Shrine in Shanghai*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.

– Source 2: Kong Yuqi 孔毓圻, chief comp. and Sun Hong 孫鎡, comp., *Kongzhai zhi 孔宅志* (Gazetteer of Kongzhai), 1724.

– Source 3: Julia K. Murray, "A Heavenly Aura: Confucian Modes of Relic Veneration," *Journal of the British Academy*, 2 (2014): 59-99. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5871/jba/002.059>.

Notes: These are specifically about Kongzhai.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://hdl.loc.gov/loc.asian/lcnclscd.2012402603>

– Source 1 Description: Digital reproduction of a 19th-century reissue of Sun Hong's 1724 *Kongzhai zhi 孔宅志* in the U.S. Library of Congress

– Source 2 URL: http://academics.hamilton.edu/asian_studies/home/CultTemp/

– Source 2 Description: "Cult of Confucius" website created by Professor Thomas A. Wilson and Stephanie Wong of Hamilton College

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: No. However, the only remains that survive on the site are two ancient ginkgo trees

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: Originally the area was completely rural and remained so until the 1990s. Since the late 1990s, Shanghai's industrial development has enveloped the site, which is now a field that is empty but for two officially protected old ginkgo trees.

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: The site is surrounded by warehouses and industrial buildings, but they have not been allowed to encroach on the field in which the two ginkgo trees stand.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Notes: Kongzhai is now part of Shanghai, but is located on the outer NW edge.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: The setting was formerly very rural, but with recent development the surrounding area is largely industrial

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Before the early 2000s there were small villages nearby, but they were moved to make way for industrial development

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Kongzhai was on a waterway, the Daying pu 大盈浦, connecting it to other waterways in the region. Most visitors came by boat, even in the earlier part of the 20th century.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: Explanations of its origins claim that Kong-surnamed descendants of Confucius built a temple for ancestral worship after settling here (and allegedly burying his robe and cap).

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Notes: All that remains at the former site of Kongzhai are two old ginkgo trees, which have been designated with official protection status. The structures that survived to the mid-20th century were demolished in the Cultural Revolution (1966). However, enough remained of Kongzhai's main hall for it to be moved several miles away and reconstructed (probably with embellishments) in 1983, but its original identity was allegedly "forgotten" until 2008. For more on the structures that formerly stood at Kongzhai, see the section "Design and Material Remains."

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: As at many other temples and administrative structures, a shrine to the Local Earth God (Tudi ci 土地祠) was associated with Kongzhai, located south of the enclosure.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: There was a separate building, associated with Kongzhai but outside its south wall, for sacrifices to Guandi 關帝, Wenchang 文昌, and Kuixing 奎星.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: "Commemorate" is not quite the right word, but Kongzhai (literally "residence of Kongs") was thought to have originated with people surnamed Kong, considered to be descendants of Confucius, who would have offered ancestral rites at Kongzhai in much earlier times. In the late 17th century, Kongzhai's literati patrons established contact with the Duke for Perpetuating the Sage (Yansheng gong 衍聖公, the head of the Kong clan in Qufu) and requested that he designate a Kong descendant to serve as official sacrificer (fengsi 奉祀) at Kongzhai. Although it took several decades to establish this arrangement officially, Kongs began coming to the area in the meantime. By the mid-19th century, there were so many that a school was founded exclusively for their sons.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: Local literati and officials

Notes: Local literati, usually in cooperation with officials serving a term in the area, sponsored most of the construction, embellishments, and repairs

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Men

– Other [specify]: If any information is recorded about buildings, only the sponsors are named, not the workers who did the construction.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Notes: The alleged burial of Confucius's robe and cap by a 34th-generation descendant ultimately

resulted in the creation of Kongzhai; however, an important stimulus for its much later development was the late 12th-century discovery of ancient jades in the area, and the dredging up of a 9th c. tomb epitaph mentioning a place called "Kongzi zhai", from a nearby river.

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The alleged burial of the robe and cap of Confucius, by a 34th-generation descendant, perhaps in 606 CE.

Notes: The burial is mentioned only in much later documents, and it could be considered legendary. However, the creation of a ritual complex in the late Ming was premised on belief that the unseen relics had indeed been buried there.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: Usually one or two local literati led the periodic effort to build, enhance, or restore facilities at Kongzhai, but they also recruited local officials to cooperate. Subscription campaigns to raise funds, and petitions to change taxation requirements are described in the Gazetteer of Kongzhai.

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The patrons of Kongzhai were all men, some of them officials or at least degree-holders, but all were highly educated in Confucian texts and principles.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: multiple motivations

Notes: Expression of devotion to Confucius was a major motivation; another was the desire of patrons to gain greater prominence and respect for themselves and for the locality, which was decidedly off the beaten track.

– Other [specify]: originally, a family temple for Kong descendants

Notes: The place-name "Kongzhai" (or "Kongzi zhai") was understood to reflect Kong descendants' having lived there in much earlier times (specifically, the Sui-Tang period), and they would have needed a temple for their ancestral worship. A nearby temple to the father of Confucius was considered additional evidence.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 800 CE

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: It is important to remember that the site no longer exists; hence the answers in this section refer to Kongzhai's configurations in the past.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Notes: The structures were associated with the Tomb of the Robe and Cap, a manmade, above-ground structure. This does not seem to meet the definition of a "landscape feature."

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: In some of its iterations, Kongzhai had covered corridors that linked up with some of the buildings.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The most important structures in the 17th century were the Tomb of the Robe and Cap (Yiguan mu 衣冠墓 or -zhong 塚), and the main sacrificial hall (Zheng dian 正殿); other buildings included a shrine for the father of Confucius (Qisheng ci 啟聖祠), a shrine for meritorious local patrons (Baogong ci 報功祠), a library, lecture hall, various studios, and kiosks. After the Kangxi emperor's bequest of calligraphy in 1705, another important building, the two-story Tower of Imperial Calligraphy (Yushu lou 御書樓), was added to house it. After a decree by the Yongzheng emperor in 1723, the Qisheng ci was replaced by the Chongsheng ci 崇聖祠 for worshipping five generations of Confucius's ancestors.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: Local earth was used initially to build a mound to commemorate (and make "visible") the burial of the robe and cap, and it was later faced with stone.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

Notes: Fired clay roof-tiles only

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know
Notes: Probably locally sourced.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Notes: It seems likely that the stone was sourced locally, as its provenance is never mentioned; moreover, the modest levels of patronage would suggest keeping expenses down by using readily available materials.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None that I know of

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: fired clay tiles for the roofs

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: Some stone tablets carved with images and/or texts were inserted into the walls of some of the buildings at Kongzhai, but they could be and sometimes were moved to other buildings. The purpose of such display was probably more inspirational than decorative.

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Incised stone tablets of various sizes (described under other headings here) were

installed on the walls of various buildings for display, but they sometimes were moved around.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Confucius and some of his disciples were represented in the main hall as sculptural icons, to serve as the focus of offerings, so were not really "decorative." More appropriately called "decorative" but also pious and inspirational were the two-dimensional portrayals of Confucius and Zhu Xi 朱熹 (1130-1200) that were donated at various times in the 17th and 18th centuries and displayed on the walls of other buildings. Figures obviously were depicted in the incised pictorial biography of the life of Confucius.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: In some scenes of Confucius's pictorial biography, there are oxen, sheep, horses, birds, and a qilin 麒麟 (a scaly, single-horned quadruped)

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Notes: Varying numbers of statues stood in the main hall, depending both on local preferences and changes in official regulations for Confucian ritual.

Reference: Wilson, Thomas A.. "Chronology of Enshrinment". Cult of Confucius, 2010.
https://academics.hamilton.edu/asian_studies/home/CultTemp/sitePages/chronology.html.

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: The main sacrificial hall had statues of Confucius and different numbers of disciples at various times in history. The 1631 Gazetteer of Songjiang Prefecture (Songjiang fuzhi 松江府志, 46:2a) says that he had been flanked by Yan Hui 顏回 and Zengzi 曾子 before Zi Lu 子路 was added, after the latter was credited with miraculously saving Kongzhai from pirates in the mid-16th century. In the 17th-18th centuries, Confucius was accompanied by the Four Correlates (si pei 四配 = Yan Hui, Zengzi, Zi Si 子思, and Mengzi 孟子), as well as Zi Lu. In 1840, copies of the statues of the Twelve Savants (shi'er zhe 十二哲) in the Qufu temple were added (1879 Qingpu xianzhi 青浦縣志, 11:2a). The statues were destroyed in the 1950s (Guo Xuehuan 郭学焕, Kongzi houyi zai Zhejiang 孔子后裔在浙江 [Hangzhou, 2013], p. 37.)

Reference: Wilson, Thomas A.. "Chronology of Enshrinement". Cult of Confucius, 2010.
https://academics.hamilton.edu/asian_studies/home/CultTemp/sitePages/chronology.html.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: See under "Cult statues"

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

Notes: However, incised tablets illustrating events in the life of Confucius were displayed at Kongzhai from 1682 until the mid-20th century, and their compositions can be traced back to a painted prototype from the mid 15th century.

Reference: Murray, Julia K.. *The Aura of Confucius: Relics and Representations of the Sage at the Kongzhai Shrine in Shanghai*. Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press, 2021. p.102-127

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Brief entries in the Gazetteer of Kongzhai record two hanging-scroll paintings of Confucius that were presented to Kongzhai; one in about 1640 and the other in 1713, but they are are not known to have survived.

Notes: The painting given in about 1640 was probably the model for an image incised on a stone tablet depicting Confucius at leisure, which bore an encomium by Wu Ercheng 吳爾成 (jinshi 1604), transcribed by the famous calligrapher Dong Qichang 董其昌 (1555-1636). The tablet was installed in the wall of a building at Kongzhai. Although it does not appear to be extant, rubbings of the stone have survived (for one example, see http://kanji.zinbun.kyoto-u.ac.jp/db-machine/imgsrv/takuhon/type_b/html/sin0384x.html).

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: Monumental inscriptions written in brush calligraphy by the Kangxi emperor for Kongzhai in 1705 were immediately reproduced as carved tablets for display, while the originals were preserved in a new Hall of Imperial Calligraphy. In a sense these reproductions were "ornamental". More clearly ornamental was a set of stone tablets carved in 1693 with the text of the Classic of Filial Piety (Xiaojing) as transcribed by the great Ming calligrapher Dong Qichang 董其昌 (1555-1636), based on a handscroll in an early Qing patron's collection; the display also included three colophons - Dong's own, dated 1631, one by an early Qing local calligrapher composed for the 1693 donation, and one by the donor himself.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: From the late 17th century onward there was a merit shrine commemorating patrons of Kongzhai, presumably inscribed with their names; and a 1717-dated text commemorating the rebuilding of this shrine was carved on a stone tablet and displayed; it is extant. Commemorative inscriptions for Kongzhai sent by two Dukes for Perpetuating the Sage (head of Kong lineage in Qufu) were also carved on stone tablets for display. The tablet with the text sent by Duke Kong Yuqi 孔毓圻 (1656-1723) was carved in 1701 and is extant; a transcription in simplified characters with punctuation and annotation appears in *Qingpu beike* 青浦碑刻 (Shanghai, 1998), pp. 104-110. The text sent by Duke Kong Qingrong 孔慶鎔 (1787-1841) in 1840 was carved in 1849, but the stone was destroyed in the Cultural Revolution; a transcription in simplified characters with punctuation and annotation appears in *Qingpu beike*, pp. 176-182.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense - see notes under previous answer.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Ceremonial gates and arches were inscribed

Notes: In 1610 a wooden arch inscribed "Gate of the Tomb of the Robe and Cap of the Exalted Sage" (Xuansheng Yiguan mumen 宣聖衣冠墓門) was erected near the boat landing leading to Kongzhai, later replaced by a stone arch inscribed "Little Queli" (Xiao Queli 小闕里), proclaiming Kongzhai to be a microcosm of Qufu's ritual complex.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: portraits and pictorial biographies of Confucius, and a portrait of Zhu Xi, which were carved on stone tablets and inset in walls.

Reference: Murray, Julia K. "'competing Lives of Confucius: The Shengji Tu at Kongzhai'". In *On Telling Images of China: Essays in Narrative Painting and Visual Culture*, Edited by Shane McCausland and Yin Hwang., 31-60. Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press, 2014.

Reference: Murray, Julia K.. *The Aura of Confucius: Relics and Representations of the Sage at*

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: The presence of figural icons of Confucius and certain disciples inside the main hall after the Jiajing emperor's 1530 ritual reform banned such images was very unusual, but it could be justified by asserting connections with the ancestral cult in Qufu.

Reference: Sommer, Deborah A.. "Destroying Confucius: Iconoclasm in the Confucian Temple". In *On Sacred Grounds: Culture, Society, Politics and the Formation of the Cult of Confucius*, edited by Thomas A. Wilson, 95-133. Cambridge, MA: Harvard East Asia Center, 2002. p.95-133

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: A set of stone tablets incised with annotated pictures of events in the life of Confucius, titled Pictures of the Traces of the Sage Confucius (Kongzi Shengji zhi tu 孔子聖蹟之圖), was made in 1610 from rubbings of the original 1444 compilation. These tablets got scattered during the Qing conquest but were reassembled (with some replacements) by a local patron. In the meantime, a local magistrate sponsored an entirely new set of tablets with more contemporary-looking pictures and fancier title, Pictures of the Great Completer, Ultimate Sage, and Culture-Exalted Former Teacher Traveling Around (Dacheng zhisheng wenxuan xianshi zhouliu zhi tu 大成至聖文宣先師周流之圖). Both sets were completed in 1682.

Reference: Murray, Julia K. "'competing Lives of Confucius: The Shengji Tu at Kongzhai'". In *On Telling Images of China: Essays in Narrative Painting and Visual Culture*, Edited by Shane McCausland and Yin Hwang., 31-60. Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press, 2014.

Reference: Murray, Julia K.. *The Aura of Confucius: Relics and Representations of the Sage at the Kongzhai Shrine in Shanghai*. Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press, 2021. p.102-127

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The unique feature of Kongzhai's iconography was its above-ground Tomb of the Robe and Cap (衣冠墓)

Notes: Over the course of the 17th century, to mark the alleged burial, an earthen mound was built and faced with stone, and a pavilion was erected on top to house a stone stele giving the name.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: In a special sense: Confucius's robe and cap were purportedly buried here by a much later descendant.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Notes: Again, just in a special sense: Confucius was worshiped as a timeless sage, not because he was dead.

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: Figures worshiped: Confucius, several of his disciples and followers, and the 34th-generation Kong descendant who allegedly buried the robe and cap.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

Notes: Confucius was not "deified" as such, although he could be considered a transcendent being and his cult was on the register of official rituals. Some apocryphal stories and Kong family legends attributed supernatural powers to him. At the end of the Qing dynasty, there was a movement to establish a religion of "Confucianism" with Confucius as its founder, comparable to Jesus in Christianity.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although there are rumors on the internet that the robe and cap have been preserved, there is no record that they had ever been seen, even in earlier ages. An accidental discovery of some ancient jade ornaments in the late 12th century led some people to suggest that these had also belonged to Confucius. In any case, the actual grave of Confucius was in Qufu, Shandong province, so such items might not really qualify as "grave goods" at all.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Although Confucius was included in the official register of state sacrifices, along with gods, he himself was not considered a god. Nonetheless, when sacrifices were performed at Kongzhai, his spirit was believed to receive them; moreover, some people wrote that he was present at Kongzhai because

of the buried robe and cap.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: When an offering ceremony was held, the spirits were invited to come and enjoy the sacrificial foods and prayers, suggesting that they were not considered to be present at other times. However, some visitors to Kongzhai wrote of experiencing a sense of Confucius's presence, and the alleged burial of his clothing relics was sometimes said to have made the region special. The 1631 Gazetteer of Songjiang Prefecture (Songjiang fuzhi 松江府志, 46:2a and 48:1b-2b) records several tales attributing miraculous events to this presence .

Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Sacrifices were offered by local literati and officials into the early 20th century, and local Kong descendants continued their observances until the founding of the officially atheistic People's Republic in 1949. For some sense of what the respective sacrifices might have been like (although much less grand), see the description of rituals in Qufu by Thomas A. Wilson, "The Cultic Confucius in the Imperial Temple and Ancestral Shrine," in Michael Nylan and Thomas A. Wilson, *Lives of Confucius: Civilization's Greatest Sage Through the Ages* (New York: Doubleday Religion, 2010), pp. 165-191.

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: The liturgy preserved in the 18th-century edition of the *Gazetteer of Kongzhai* (*Kongzhai zhi* 孔宅志 6:7a-8b) includes diagrams of the items to be offered during a sacrifice, among which are a sheep and a pig, along with wine, vegetables, grains, etc. The diagram is prescriptive and should not be taken as proof of actual practice.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: wine, various foodstuffs, cloth, incense

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Various items were given to Kongzhai on occasion.

Notes: E.g., the Kangxi emperor's personal gift of his calligraphy in 1705, mentioned in an earlier section. Auspicious objects for which Kongzhai was considered an appropriate place were also donated, such as a jade chime-stone (1706), an ancient bronze wine container (1707), and a set of eight ancient bronze bells and earthenware beaker from a nearby excavation (1713); recorded in the 18th-century edition of the Gazetteer of Kongzhai (Kongzhai zhi 孔宅志, 5:15a).

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: When a magistrate was newly arrived in office, the local literati might pressure him to conduct a sacrifice at Kongzhai; otherwise participation in sacrifices there was voluntary (and sporadic). It is important to note that Kongzhai was not part of the empire-wide network of Confucian temples that were associated with government schools in administrative centers, where an official conducted the ritual and students and local degree-holders were expected to attend.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

Notes: Maintenance sponsored by local literati or officials was voluntary, and sporadic, but it was "required" in the sense that the facilities quickly deteriorated if neglected. Land associated with Kongzhai was supposed to provide resources with which to fund maintenance. There are a few vague references to a Buddhist monk living on the premises to serve as "guardian."

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably, sweeping the courtyards, etc.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: There was a recurrent but sporadic pattern of building, deterioration (or outright destruction), and reconstruction over the centuries.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Notes: There does not seem to have been a "permanent staff" , although the Kong descendants who served as sacrificer may have been considered responsible for taking care of Kongzhai.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Kongzhai would periodically attract attention and a rise in local patronage, flourish for a while, then suffer decline from neglect or even destruction.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Individual officials and other literati came to Kongzhai, but there was no organized pilgrimage as such. It was not well known outside the region.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Large-scale rituals (i.e., the shidian 釋奠) were expensive and rare, probably occurring only around the times when Kongzhai was "discovered" by a higher authority, such as the Kangxi emperor in 1705, and given resources for more elaborate performance of the semi-annual sacrifice to Confucius. A relatively well-recorded major celebration was held at Kongzhai for the birthday of Confucius in 1914, which drew prominent men from Shanghai city; they chose to celebrate it in Kongzhai because an outbreak of fighting made it difficult to travel to Qufu, as they had done in 1913. (A volume of prose accounts and poems related to this 1914 birthday celebration is *Poems on Kongzhai* [Kongzhai shi 孔宅詩], Yao Wendong 姚文棟, comp. Shanghai, 1915.)

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: As at Confucian temples associated with government schools, sacrifices at Kongzhai were meant to be offered twice a year, but it is hard to know how rigorously this was done, and resources often were lacking. A routine sacrifice would not have included animals, just wine and other foods.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: We do not know.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: twice a year, in the second months of spring and autumn

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: An entire chapter of the 18th-century edition of the *Gazetteer of Kongzhai* (Kongzhai zhi 孔宅志, juan 6) describes the correct procedures, which were very similar to rituals at official Confucian temples.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably the person designated as head sacrificer made sure that things were done correctly. After the early 18th century, a Kong descendant held the hereditary position of sacrificer at Kongzhai.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Kongzhai presumably followed the liturgy of the Confucian shidian 釋奠 sacrifice, which included music and ritual dancing, as well as intoning of prayers (see Kongzhai zhi 孔宅志, juan 6).

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Alcohol is one of the offerings, but not drunk by participants during the ceremony.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Initially, no; but the situation changed after the appointment of a hereditary Kong sacrificer.

↳ Present full time

– No

Notes: Up until the appointment of a Kong descendant to move to Kongzhai and serve as sacrificer, various local literati took charge of the rituals.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1746 CE

– Yes

Notes: The Ministry of Rites formally approved an official, hereditary position as sacrificer at Kongzhai in 1746 for a line of Kong descendants registered in Qingpu. The last incumbent served well into the 20th century.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1746 CE - 1949 CE

↳ Present part time

– No

Notes: The Kong descendant serving as sacrificer lived in or near Kongzhai, certainly after the position was confirmed in 1746, and possibly somewhat earlier while it was being negotiated.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1746 CE - 1949 CE

– Yes

Notes: Until the confirmation of a Kong descendant as sacrificer, local literati or a serving official came to Kongzhai to conduct the rites.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1746 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They were probably all members of the Han majority, but their ethnicity was not recorded.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: The sacrifices were performed by the educated elite -- officials and other literati -- who probably took turns directing the rites. They continued to participate even after Kong descendants took charge (possibly starting in the 1720s but certainly by 1746). It is not clear how well educated the Kong sacrificers were, but they held the rank of Erudite of the Five Classics (Wujing boshi 五經博士), the same as the eldest son and younger brother of the Kong duke in Qufu.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: The only people who were officially dedicated to Kongzhai for life were the Kong descendants who served as sacrificer (perhaps starting in the 1720s but definitely from 1746 onward).

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The Kong descendant who was designated the hereditary sacrificer had higher status than other descendants.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: The Kong sacrificer certainly lived nearby and possibly within the confines of Kongzhai itself at times. During the Taiping Rebellion in the 1860s, some Kongs were said to have appropriated some of its lesser buildings.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Notes: For a time in the late Ming-early Qing, responsibility for maintenance rotated among an unofficial roster of local literati who voluntarily chose to support Kongzhai. Lands privately donated to Kongzhai provided most of the revenue, both for maintaining the facilities and for rituals. Complaints that tenants or even managers sometimes expropriated fields for their own benefit led to a lawsuit, resulting in the lands being restored in 1716. Afterwards, the Kong descendant serving as sacrificer was presumably responsible.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: As explained under "Maintenance," operations at Kongzhai were handled somewhat ad hoc by local literati patrons before Kong descendants took over.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: Kongzhai had lands that had been donated by private patrons at various times. Details concerning donors and locations, and the lawsuit that was finally resolved in 1716, are recorded in the Gazetteer of Kongzhai (Kongzhai zhi 孔宅志), juan 8.

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Notes: Supporters of Kongzhai submitted many unsuccessful petitions, both to the dukes in Qufu and to the central government, seeking official certification and regular funding because the ad hoc arrangements were unreliable.

Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Notes: Tenants worked the lands that were donated to Kongzhai.

- ↳ Does this place lease out tools:
– Field doesn't know

Public Works

- Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: In the early 1650s, a local magistrate built a library at Kongzhai but it had burned down by 1705. The kinds of books it housed were never enumerated, but most likely included editions of the Confucian classics and perhaps literary works.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1650 CE - 1705 CE

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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